

TASKS FOR CREATING NEW TYPES OF RANGE IN CHILDREN'S CLOTHING

Khudayeva Dilafruz Gayratdjanovna.
National institute fine arts and design
named after Kamoliddin Behzod.
Teacher of the department of the clothing design.
daryabukina1705@mail.ru

Annotsatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada Bolalar kiyimini modellashtirishda to'g'ri tanlangan gazlamaning ahamiyati katta ekanligi, Trikotaj matolaridan tikilgan kiyimni kiyib yurish qulay, ergonomik talablarga javob berishi, hamda ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish masalalari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bolalar kiyimlari, trikotaj, rivojlantirish, isloh qilish, mato, to'qimachilik, ishlab chiqarish, modellashtirish.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье освещается значение правильно подобранных тканей при моделировании детской одежды, то, чтобы одежда из трикотажных полотен была комфортной в ношении и отвечала эргономическим требованиям, а также вопросы развития производства.*

Ключевые слова: *детская одежда, вязание, разработка, реформирование, ткань, текстиль, производство, моделирование.*

Annotation: *This article highlights the importance of correctly selected fabrics in modeling children's clothing, the fact that clothing made of knitted fabrics is comfortable to wear and meets ergonomic requirements, as well as issues of production development.*

Key words: *children's clothes, knitting, development, reformation, fabric, textile, production, modeling.*

The main goal of forming a market economy in Uzbekistan is the emphasis of production on the will of consumers based on the formation of effective management systems for a socially oriented economy, the creation of objective conditions for encouraging hard work, creativity, initiative, high productivity while ensuring the economic freedom of citizens. On the one hand, the market mechanism ensures the rational use of labor, material and financial resources, on the other hand, it requires the flexibility of production technologies and constant support for the achievements of scientific and technological development in economic activity.

One of the important requirements for the development of light industry is the further improvement of technology and design processes for modern children's clothing. To find solutions to the problems facing us, scientific research is being carried out on the selection of fabrics for modern children's

clothing, determining their quality indicators and designs.[1. b.12] It is possible to achieve the quality and competitiveness of manufactured clothing and knitwear products by studying and analyzing folk fashion, market stalls and the assortment of modern clothing.

Children are the joy of our family, the continuation of our future. Children, the most important aspect of life, are imitative and curious about the external environment. Children's growth is uneven. The typology of children's sizes differs significantly from the typology of an adult. Children of the same age may vary in size, and their body proportions may change as they age. The distribution of sizes and their combination in the children's group differs sharply from the normal distribution [4. b. 18]. Therefore, the typology of children's sizes is developed specifically according to a unique style.

Children's clothing has a great positive and negative impact on their minds. Clothes play an important role in shaping growing children to be fast, agile, intelligent, confident and insightful. The worldview of children is completely different from the worldview of adults. The bright color of the fabrics guarantees a rapid expansion of the range of perception in children. The importance of correctly selected slits when modeling children's clothing is very important. When choosing children's clothing, high-quality, hygienic, functional and aesthetic materials are recommended. The material used for children's clothing must be durable and practical due to children's activities. Children's clothing should serve to improve air circulation in the child's body.

Children's clothing, being the prototype of adult clothing, repeats all the details. It went through a long history of development before it acquired its current form. When designing children's clothing, various methods of drawing are used, taking into account the physique of children of each age group, the distribution of clothing parts, body sizes and seam allowances. Although design methods have their drawbacks, they allow relatively accurate determination of the shape and dimensions of clothing parts and are still used to calculate the necessary data for preliminary drawings. The most famous of them are the size calculation method, the proportional calculation method, the coordinate method, the scale method, etc. In many sewing processes, proportional calculation methods were used for the first time. These methods are a type of calculation and measurement methods; where cutting dimensions are replaced by calculated dimensions. The calculated sizes are determined in proportion to the two main dimensional designations, taking into account the second size of the chest semicircle and proportionality to height [6. p.45]. The increase in the number of forms and styles of children's clothing is closely related to the increase in the types and forms of adult clothing.

One of the main indicators of the quality of modern children's clothing is its functionality. The functionality of clothing is a general concept that includes the design and aesthetic characteristics of clothing, physiological, social and technological requirements. Young children's clothing should be very loose, uncomplicated and comfortable. The first layer of children's clothing should be frost-resistant, light, fairly straight, and sleeveless. The bottom layer is blouses

and shirts with sleeves, most often made of knitwear. As the child grows up, the type of clothing he wears also changes: overalls, jackets, raincoats, among others.

Trousers, shirts and jackets are recommended for preschool boys. The boys' coat has raglan sleeves: the placket fastens in the middle. There are pockets and a belt. It is known that knitwear is a fabric or product consisting of loops. The loop is the main element of a knitted fabric or product and is a shape caused by the bending of the thread.

Based on the existing classification, knitted products are divided into outerwear, innerwear, socks, gloves, hats and scarves. Each listed group includes subgroups such as seasonal clothing and sportswear. There are mainly knitting, semi-regular and regular methods for producing knitted products, and in some cases a mixed method is used, including knitting and regular methods [4.p.58].

The production of children's clothing, despite the high level of competition from thousands of retail stores and online stores, will be relevant in format in medium-sized and large cities. There is a certain target audience that prefers custom-made clothes. In addition, the buyer has the opportunity to order the style, design and decor of children's clothing as desired. Based on the above requirements, it is possible to create a highly profitable enterprise by starting the production of children's clothing, because in children's clothing it should be paid attention to quality, comfort and color. Only then can it become one of the customer-oriented consumer goods.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yhati

1. Abdukarimov B.X. va boshqalar. Korxonalar iqtisodiyoti: Darslik. – T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2013.

2. Благодаров А.В. Технология стратегического управления конкурентной позицией предприятия на рынке // Развитие научных концепций и технологий управления экономическими системами в современном обществе: Материалы международной научно-практической конференции 5 апреля 2004. Киров, 2004. –с. 21-23.

3. Каримова Д.А. Развитие швейного производства в условиях многоукладной экономики (на материалах Республики Узбекистан): Автореф. дисс. канд. экон. наук. –Т.: ТГТУ, 2002. –20 с.

4. Sayfutdinov M.A. Tikuvchilik korxonalari marketing strategiyasini ishlab chiqish: Iqtisod fanlari nomzodi... dis. TDIU. –T.: 2004. – 170 b

5. Михайлов О.В. Основы мировой конкурентоспособности. – М.: Познавательная книга плюс, 1999 г. –592 с.

6. Yusupov S.Sh. Kuchli raqobat sharoitida O'zbekiston to'qimachilik korxonalari rivojlanish strategiyasining asosiy yo'nalishlari. Monografiya. –T.: "Fan va texnologiya", 2013. –152 bet.

7. Манзура Р.А., Бахромжон Д.Б., Зухра Б.А. Использование практично – декоративных украшений в национальных костюмах. East European Scientific Journal (Warsaw, Poland) 2019 part 6, 13-16. https://eesajournal.com/wp-content/uploads/EESA_journal_6_part_0-1.pdf

8. Parpiev,U.M.; Dadamirzayev,B.B.; Urinova,S. Analysis Of Vibration Effects On Sewing Machines. The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research (ISSN–2642-7478) Published:January 31, 2021| Pages:65-69 Doi: <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajjir/Volume03Issue01-11>